

The importance of developing strength qualities in wrestling, considering their specialization to the structure of technical components for each technique performed in horizontal and vertical planes

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Abstract

Purpose: The objective of the study was to determine the dynamics of general physical fitness indicators in qualified 200-meter sprinters.

Results: The results obtained from the final testing stage are as follows: in the one-minute rope skipping test, the experimental group recorded 130.29 ± 19.53 repetitions, whereas the control group demonstrated 126.43 ± 18.47 repetitions. These findings indicate that the difference between the groups is not statistically significant.

The mathematical and statistical analysis applied in assessing the general physical fitness indicators of 200 m runners yielded positive outcomes, confirming that the relative differences between the groups were minimal.

Methods: The study employed the following methods: analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical control, pedagogical testing, and pedagogical experiment.

Conclusion: The complex application of strength and speed development exercises, jumping drills, sprint exercises, interval running, and general conditioning exercises leads to a significant improvement in students' physical qualities. This contributes not only to enhanced athletic performance but also to the formation of a healthy lifestyle. In conclusion, the systematic and scientifically grounded development of general physical fitness in 200-meter sprinter students is a key prerequisite for improving athletic mastery, expanding functional capabilities, and achieving consistently high performance outcomes.

Keywords: 200-meter running, sprinting, athletics, student-athletes, general physical fitness, special physical fitness, physical qualities, speed, speed-strength, explosive strength, general endurance, speed endurance, muscular strength, starting speed

Introduction

The 200-meter sprint, as one of the short-distance events in athletics, is a discipline that requires a complex integration of high speed, speed-strength, special endurance, and coordination of movement. Compared to the 100-meter sprint, this event demands not only the achievement of maximal speed but also the ability to maintain that speed over a longer distance. This, in turn, is directly dependent on the level of general physical fitness of 200-meter sprinters.

In modern athletics, achieving high competitive results in the 200-meter event depends

on the optimal development of general physical fitness components—namely strength, speed, endurance, agility, and flexibility—as well as on the proper planning dynamics of training processes and annual training cycles. Particularly during the pre-competition phase, the targeted development of general physical fitness indicators plays a decisive role in determining the effectiveness of subsequent specialized preparation.

An analysis of scientific literature indicates that, although a considerable number of studies have been conducted on the special physical preparation of qualified 200-meter sprinters, there is still insufficient research focusing on the comprehensive evaluation of the seasonal and stage-by-stage dynamics of general physical fitness indicators in athletes specializing specifically in the 200-meter distance. This gap creates certain challenges in scientifically managing the pre-competition training process, in differentiating training loads during preparation for 200-meter competitions, and in predicting competitive performance outcomes.

Therefore, the study of general physical fitness indicators in qualified 200-meter sprinters, the identification of their dynamic changes during the pre-competition phase and throughout the training cycle, and the development of practical recommendations are of significant scientific and practical importance.

According to L.V. Smuragina, an analysis of the literature related to the dynamics of general physical fitness in 200-meter sprinters and short-distance runners shows that, although there is no sufficiently in-depth analysis specifically focused on general physical fitness in 200-meter athletes, a number of studies have investigated motor qualities, general and special physical preparation, and annual training cycles in sprint events.

Results and discussion

Furthermore, several researchers at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Educa-

Table 1. General physical fitness indicators and their statistical characteristics recorded at the initial stage of the pedagogical experiment in the experimental group of qualified student-athletes in athletics (n = 14)

Participants	Standing Long Jump (m)	Standing Triple Jump (m)	Five-Step Jump (m)	3 kg Medicine Ball Overhead Throw (m)	3000 m Run (sec)	Rope Skipping (1 min, reps)
T.U.	2.16	6.23	10.72	9.46	882.6	118
T.A.	2.25	5.86	9.43	8.74	793.5	133
S.M.	2.17	6.81	11.34	9.85	892.7	124
U.N.	2.34	5.68	9.63	7.97	770.5	136
I.J.	2.13	6.17	11.04	9.64	834.6	117
O.Z.	2.31	5.95	8.83	8.63	906.4	135
X.Z.	2.15	6.58	11.08	10.07	771.2	114
A.G.	2.38	5.63	10.34	8.17	879.4	145
Ch.S.	2.24	6.49	9.37	7.66	767.5	121
R.J.	2.32	5.74	11.48	9.35	894.7	131
O.I.	2.37	7.55	8.74	8.23	762.6	155
Sh.X.	2.14	6.22	10.23	10.27	936.8	137
N.N.	2.23	6.57	9.32	7.13	773.5	121
A.O.	2.21	5.73	10.05	9.95	847.6	137

tion and Sports have conducted studies on the development of general physical fitness indicators in short-distance runners. These works highlight the development of key physical qualities—such as strength, speed, and endurance—and serve as a theoretical foundation for understanding the pedagogical and methodological aspects of training, as well as the dynamics of general physical fitness in 200-meter sprinters.

Leading scholars have also emphasized that proper planning of physical preparation is crucial in preparing 200-meter runners for competition. They have provided recommendations on the planning, testing, and management of physical training processes for short-distance runners. According to M.S. Olimov, the 200-meter sprint, as a short-distance running event, involves the comparative analysis of the effects of special physical preparation and the evaluation of training methodologies. This research emphasizes the importance of monitoring general physical fitness (GPF) in 200-meter athletes during the pre-competition phase and highlights the role of specialized exercises in improving athletes' motor performance indicators.

According to the recommendations of O.K. Khudayberganov, the preparation of 200-meter runners for competitions should include an analysis of the dynamic changes in key per-

formance indicators, such as speed, speed-strength, and specific physical work capacity.

The present study is aimed at determining the general physical fitness (GPF) indicators of student-athletes specializing in the 200-meter sprint, assessing their levels of speed, strength, endurance, and speed-strength qualities, and developing scientific and methodological approaches for their improvement.

In order to enhance the effectiveness of preparing qualified 200-meter sprinters for competitions, it is essential to consider their general physical fitness indicators alongside their individual characteristics. The appropriate selection of training means and methods, aligned with clearly defined training objectives, contributes to achieving high athletic performance and further improves athletes' readiness for competition.

Although 200-meter runners demonstrate strong performance in local competitions, participation in major international events requires a higher level of athletic achievement, indicating the need for further improvement.

Based on a comparative analysis of the initial stage of the study conducted with highly qualified 200-meter sprinters, the following results were obtained.

At the initial stage of testing, the general physical fitness indicators of student-athletes

Table 2. General physical fitness indicators and their statistical characteristics recorded at the initial stage of the pedagogical experiment in the control group of qualified student-athletes in athletics (n = 14)

Participants	Standing Long Jump (m)	Standing Triple Jump (m)	Five-Step Jump (m)	3 kg Medicine Ball Over-head Throw (m)	3000 m Run (sec)	Rope Skipping (1 min, reps)
A.M.	2.18	5.86	10.35	8.38	874.0	116
A.H.	2.06	7.36	10.96	8.92	808.3	125
A.I.	2.49	6.13	9.37	9.46	894.0	133
B.D.	2.25	6.71	10.24	8.35	784.5	118
G.J.	2.51	5.77	11.05	8.97	835.8	136
K.K.	2.08	6.80	10.02	9.55	895.5	117
T.O.	2.24	5.56	9.73	7.98	813.7	123
O.Sh.	2.07	6.89	11.17	8.25	887.5	128
X.B.	2.35	5.32	10.62	8.74	756.2	131
A.Z.	2.17	6.85	10.13	8.16	884.3	137
E.M.	2.49	5.68	9.31	9.43	803.4	129
T.E.	2.12	6.76	10.23	8.65	879.4	119
N.N.	2.43	6.22	11.03	9.26	824.7	131
Y.S.	2.24	6.77	10.42	8.64	833.5	127

specializing in the 200-meter sprint were recorded as follows:

In the standing long jump test, the experimental group achieved an average result of 2.24 ± 0.31 m, while the control group recorded 2.26 ± 0.31 m. The absolute difference between the groups was minimal, indicating no statistically significant variation. This suggests that both groups demonstrated a comparable level of lower-body explosive strength at the initial stage of the study.

Similarly, in the standing triple jump test, the experimental group obtained a result of 6.23 ± 0.93 m, whereas the control group recorded 6.33 ± 0.92 m. The observed difference between the groups was minor, further confirming that the athletes' speed-strength capabilities were relatively homogeneous prior to the intervention.

In the five-step jump test, the control group achieved 10.33 ± 1.40 m, while the experimental group recorded 10.11 ± 1.41 m. Both absolute and relative differences remained small and statistically insignificant, indicating that multi-step explosive coordination and power characteristics were similarly developed across both groups.

In the 3 kg medicine ball overhead throw (two-handed forward throw), the experimental group achieved 8.94 ± 1.43 m, while the control group recorded 8.77 ± 1.36 m, reflecting comparable upper-body strength and coordination levels. The negligible difference between the groups once again supports the assumption of baseline equivalence.

Furthermore, in the 3000-meter running test, which reflects general endurance capacity, the experimental group demonstrated a result of 836.69 ± 116.77 seconds, whereas the control group recorded 847.58 ± 115.42 seconds. Although the experimental group showed slightly better performance, the difference was not statistically significant, indicating similar endurance levels in both groups.

Overall, the results of the initial testing stage indicate that the general physical fitness levels of both the experimental and control groups were relatively similar. This homogeneity between groups is crucial, as it confirms the validity of subsequent comparisons and ensures that any changes observed in later stages of the study can be attributed to the applied training interventions rather than pre-existing differences.

Table 3. Comparison of the statistical characteristics of general physical fitness indicators recorded at the initial stage of the pedagogical experiment between the control (n = 14) and experimental (n = 14) groups of qualified student-athletes in athletics

Test	Experimental Group (\bar{X})	σ	V (%)	Control Group (\bar{X})	σ	V (%)	Absolute Difference (AD)	Relative Difference (RD)	t-value	p-value
Standing Long Jump (m)	2.24	0.31	13.97	2.26	0.31	13.61	0.02	0.89	0.17	>0.8
Standing Triple Jump (m)	6.23	0.93	14.99	6.33	0.93	14.60	0.10	1.69	0.30	>0.7
Five-Step Jump (m)	10.11	1.41	13.98	10.33	1.41	13.62	0.22	2.14	0.41	>0.6
3 kg Medicine Ball Overhead Throw (m)	8.94	1.43	15.97	8.77	1.37	15.60	0.17	1.90	0.32	>0.7
3000 m Run (sec)	836.69	116.77	13.96	847.58	115.42	13.62	10.90	1.30	0.25	>0.8
Rope Skipping (1 min, reps)	130.29	19.53	14.99	126.43	18.47	14.61	3.86	2.96	0.54	>0.5

Conclusion

The general physical fitness (GPF) of student-athletes specializing in the 200-meter sprint is one of the key determinants of their athletic performance and functional capacity.

Fig. Relative differences in general physical fitness indicators between experimental and control groups at the initial stage

Research indicates that the balanced development of physical qualities—such as speed, speed-strength, endurance, agility, and flexibility—plays a crucial role in achieving high per-

formance in sprint events. In particular, for the 200-meter distance, alongside speed and speed-strength, an adequate level of specific endurance is essential.

The conducted analyses revealed that general physical fitness indicators among student-athletes are not uniform, highlighting the need for their systematic and progressive development. The appropriate combination of general and special physical training methods, scientifically grounded planning of training loads, and the implementation of an individualized approach contribute significantly to achieving high training effectiveness.

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